

Hydrokinetic energy site selection under high seasonality: The i-IHE index

R. Carballo^a, D.M. Fouz^{a,*}, I. López^a, G. Iglesias^{b,c}

^a Área de Ingeniería Hidráulica, EPSE, Campus Terra, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, 27002, Lugo, Spain

^b School of Engineering and Architecture & MaREI, Environmental Research Institute, University College Cork, College Road, P43 C573, Cork, Ireland

^c School of Engineering, Computing and Mathematics, University of Plymouth, Marine Building, Drake Circus, PL4 8AA, Plymouth, UK

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Hydrokinetic energy
Tidal power
River inputs
Intra-annual variability
Numerical modelling

ABSTRACT

A novel index is developed to select sites for hydrokinetic energy exploitation in coastal areas with high resource seasonality – the typical case being estuaries whose hydrodynamics are highly influenced by variable river discharges. The intra-annual Integrated Hydrokinetic Energy (i-IHE) index is constructed by means of a new penalty function that modifies the Integrated Hydrokinetic Energy (IHE) index. The i-IHE index thus defined is applied to a case study: the Miño Estuary (NW Iberian Peninsula), with seasonal variations of up to 1000 % in the riverine discharge. The hydrodynamics are modelled by the state-of-the-art Delft3D-FLOW code using a high-resolution 2DH grid. The results confirm a strong variability in the resource, with time periods shorter than seasons. The results obtained for the penalty function throughout the Miño Estuary, with values ranging between 0.5 and 0.75, show the relevance of the i-IHE index in order to not overestimate the potential of coastal areas subject to large intra-annual variability. Compared to the conventional IHE index, the novel i-IHE index highlights smaller areas with greater energy potential. The larger exploitable energy in these areas, along with the lower costs and fewer restrictions for hydrokinetic energy operation, will be of interest to developers and stakeholders.

1. Introduction

Recent climate neutrality objectives and policies highlight the commitment of public bodies towards an energy transition driven by renewable energy sources [1,2]. In this context of energy mix diversification, marine renewable energies [3,4], and in particular tidal stream and hydrokinetic energy, are considered as feasible energy resources in different coastal regions worldwide [5,6], primarily in estuarine areas subject to large tidal ranges and, under certain circumstances, river discharges [7]. The interest of estuaries for hydrokinetic energy operation results from their strong tidal currents caused by large tidal ranges, constrictions [8] and, in some cases, barotropic circulation resulting from river discharges [9,10] or, in specific coastal areas, baroclinic circulation [11,12].

Many studies have analysed the most appropriate areas for hydrokinetic energy operation in many coastal regions by considering different approaches [13–21]. For all the interest of the results obtained, most of them focus on energetic analyses, with environmental and socioeconomic aspects typically not considered in any great detail. It has been shown that the costs of installation and operation together with the

restrictions from socioeconomic activities and environmental considerations may greatly differ not only among coastal bodies but also in a given coastal area [22]. With this in view, several works have resorted to more comprehensive economic and environmental approaches when analysing areas where different zones have been proposed for energy operation [23–26]. This is of particular interest in estuaries, coastal bodies which shelter a vast number of socioeconomic activities (e.g., fishing, aquaculture, transportation), being also places of high environmental value, with different figures of protection (e.g., Natura 2000) [27,28], which may pose a threat to energy exploitation. In consequence, an appropriate decision-making process leading to the identification of the best locations for the installation of hydrokinetic energy facilities in estuarine areas should resort to comprehensive approaches considering not only the available resource, but all the different aspects affecting energy exploitation [23,29].

Although final energy project stages require an accurate farm design, for which thorough cost-benefit and environmental site-specific analyses must be developed [30,31], in early-stage projects the main issue is to reduce the uncertainties when planning the installation of a hydrokinetic farm [32]. With this in view, the Integrated Hydrokinetic Energy

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: davidmateo.fouz.varela@usc.es (D.M. Fouz).

(IHE) index has recently been proposed. Its implementation leads to the selection of the most appropriate area for energy exploitation in a coastal region irrespective of the energy conversion technology and farm layout [29]. This index is based on a holistic approach, integrating the three main aspects affecting hydrokinetic energy farm operation: (i) the exploitable energy resource (computation of the hydrokinetic energy index, HE index), (ii) the coastal configuration and their effects on the installation costs (computation of the geospatial cost penalty function, C_{gp}), and (iii) the socioeconomic and environmental aspects (computation of the geospatial water use penalty function, U_{gp}). The IHE index indicates suitability for hydrokinetic energy exploitation if $IHE \geq 1$, with larger values indicating greater suitability.

The IHE index was previously applied to identifying the most appropriate locations for energy conversion in the Shannon Estuary (W Ireland), leading to an overall improvement with respect to other, more simplistic, currently available procedures. Despite the large river discharges into the Shannon Estuary, this coastal body was shown to behave as a tidally driven waterbody, where the influence of the large fluvial inputs on the total available hydrokinetic resource is scarce, as is apparent from the virtually inexistent intra-annual variations [33]. However, in estuaries subject to large fluvial discharges and a more limited tidal prism than in the case of the Shannon Estuary, the hydrodynamics may be more affected by the discharge variability, resulting in significant intra-annual variability in the hydrokinetic energy resource (e.g. Ref. [34]). In this case, the previously proposed IHE index would not be suited, for it does not consider the intra-annual variability in the hydrokinetic resource. For this reason, its application to the above-mentioned estuaries could lead to ill-informed site selection.

In this work, a new version of the IHE index is proposed: the intra-annual IHE (i-IHE) index, which takes into account the intra-annual variability in the exploitable energy resource. This is done by extending the HE index (the energy resource related part in the IHE index), for which a new parameter accounting for the variability in the resource is computed, and leading to the i-HE index (the energy resource related part in the new i-IHE index). The approach is illustrated through a case study in the Miño Estuary (NW Iberian Peninsula) (Fig. 1), a shallow and mesotidal coastal region subject to large fluvial inputs [35], which constitutes a paradigm of seasonality in its available energy resource – its hydrodynamics are largely dominated over long periods by river discharges [14].

The Miño Estuary is subject to the large river inputs of the River Miño, the most important river in NW Spain and N Portugal, which in turn presents a significant intra-annual flow variability resulting from the precipitation patterns in this region. The largest average monthly

flows, with more than $1000 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$, occur in the first part of the year, steadily decreasing up to the last trimester, when they reach their minima, around $100 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$. On this basis, a seasonal behaviour can be described, with average seasonal differences of up to 1000 % (winter-autumn), which in turn considerably affect the hydrodynamics of the estuary, and consequently the exploitable hydrokinetic energy resource [14].

Previous works have analysed the suitability of the Miño Estuary for hydrokinetic energy exploitation from a hydrodynamic standpoint by considering the installation of third-generation hydrokinetic energy converters (HECs) (i.e., those able to operate with water depths of approx. 1.0 m, given its depth-limited configuration), identifying specific areas of interest in the inner and middle estuary [14,36]. Likewise, more recent studies also identified and demonstrated the economic viability of a tidal test site in the outer estuary [37]. Nevertheless, holistic procedures jointly encompassing the seasonality of the energy production and the analysis of socioeconomic and environmental aspects have not been previously applied to this coastal area. The comprehensive analysis of the aforementioned aspects, and in particular the results from the application of the proposed i-IHE index, will provide key information towards an informed decision-making for hydrokinetic energy exploitation in the Miño Estuary and, more generally, in estuarine areas subject to a marked intra-annual variability in their hydrokinetic energy resource.

This study is structured as follows: first, in Section 2, an overall view of the IHE index and the novel i-IHE index are described; in Section 3, the hydrodynamics of the study are accurately characterized by high-resolution numerical modelling, and on this basis the spatial distribution of HE index is computed; next, in Section 4, a thorough characterization of the intra-annual variability of the hydrodynamics in the study area leads to the computation of the proposed i-HE index; in Section 4, the C_{gp} and U_{gp} penalty functions are computed; in Section 5, the spatial distribution of the new i-IHE index is obtained by integrating the previous results. Finally, in Section 6, conclusions are drawn.

2. From IHE to i-IHE index. A general overview

The Integrated Hydrokinetic Energy (IHE) index represents a holistic tool for selecting the most appropriate locations for hydrokinetic energy exploitation in a coastal region, for which, as previously stated, the different the relevant aspects which affect the decision-making process are considered. The IHE index considers: (i) the exploitable resource, (ii) installation costs, and (iii) socioeconomic and environmental features. It is expressed as:

Fig. 1. Location of the Miño Estuary in NW Spain (a); areas of interest (AOI) for hydrokinetic energy exploitation identified in previous works and location of ADCP (b).

$$\text{IHE} = \text{HE } C_{gp} U_{gp}, \quad (1)$$

where HE is the Hydrokinetic Energy resource index, which accounts for (i) meaning HE = 1 the threshold above which hydrokinetic energy exploitation is suitable from an energetic standpoint, and C_{gp} and U_{gp} stand for the geospatial cost penalty function and geospatial water use penalty function, respectively, accounting for points (ii) and (iii), respectively, and with values ranging from 0 to 1. The HE index is defined as:

$$\text{HE} = \frac{E_e}{E_{ref}}, \quad (2)$$

where E_e is the exploitable hydrokinetic energy resource (i.e., the energy resource within the cut-in and cut-off limits of a given HEC) during a representative time period (e. g., one year) and E_{ref} the threshold energy resource level which represents the minimum energy resource required for hydrokinetic energy exploitation suitability.

As a result, the physical interpretation of the IHE index is straightforward, a larger value implying a more appropriate location for hydrokinetic energy exploitation, with values above 1 indicating suitability for hydrokinetic energy exploitation, which would correspond with a coastal area with HE = 1, i.e., the threshold value for suitability from an energetic standpoint, without considering cost and water use penalizations ($C_{gp} = 1$ and $U_{gp} = 1$).

As previously stated, IHE index is computed for a given period of time and therefore does not take into account the intra-annual variability in the hydrokinetic resource. Thus, its straightforward application to estuaries whose hydrodynamics are significantly affected by river discharges subject to intra-annual variations would lead to an ill-informed decision-making. On this basis, a new version of the IHE index is proposed, the so called intra-annual IHE (i-IHE) index, which reads:

$$\text{i-IHE} = \text{i-HE } C_{gp} U_{gp}, \quad (3)$$

where i-HE index is the intra-annual hydrokinetic energy index, which is computed as:

$$\text{i-HE} = \text{i-}E_{gp} \text{ HE}, \quad (4)$$

where $\text{i-}E_{gp}$ is a geospatial intra-annual resource variability penalty function (values ranging from 1 to 0), according to which a value of 1 indicates a location where the intra-annual variability of the resource does not impose any type of restriction or limitation to the exploitation of the hydrokinetic resource (i.e., there is virtually no intra-annual variation in the resource). This term is proposed to be computed as:

$$\text{i-}E_{gp} = 1 - \frac{\sigma(E_{e,i})}{\max(E_{e,i})}, \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma(E_{e,i})$ is the standard deviation, and $\max(E_{e,i})$ the maximum value at each grid cell of $E_{e,i}$, which represent the exploitable energy over each i time period representative of the intra-annual variation of the resource (e.g., seasons, months).

The application of any of these indexes, HE, IHE or i-IHE, leads to the definition of 5 categories (Table 1). These categories are the same for the

three indexes. This results from IHE and i-IHE indexes being obtained from HE index by applying different penalization functions (values between 0 and 1), i.e., the use of these categories for selecting areas by using the HE index would be only valid in case of the different penalization functions attaining values of 1 (no penalization). For example, using the IHE index for selecting the areas would be only valid in the case of coastal bodies with virtual or reduced intra-annual resource variability, or in other words $\text{i-}E_{gp}$ approximately equal to 1 (no penalization), as it is the case of the Shannon Estuary [33].

It is important to note that the application of the $\text{i-}E_{gp}$ function is not restricted by the coastal configuration or the hydrodynamics characteristics of the coastal body, so it can be used to analyse any coastal region of interest. The same applies to the IHE index, and therefore to the resulting i-IHE index. In the case of estuaries or other coastal areas with low resource seasonality, $\text{i-}E_{gp}$ will take on values close to unity, and thus the straightforward application of the IHE index would be valid (IHE index \approx i-IHE index).

In the following sections, the different parameters of the i-IHE index are explained in detail, with a focus on the extension of the IHE index so as to consider the intra-annual variations in the energy resource, which is illustrated through its application to the Miño Estuary.

3. Hydrokinetic energy resource (HE) index

3.1. Numerical modelling procedure and validation

The first step for obtaining the i-IHE index in a coastal region requires computing the HE index, which provides an estimation of the suitability of a given coastal area in terms of hydrokinetic energy resource. To this end, an accurate characterization of the hydrokinetic energy resource in a coastal region is required, for which a detailed description of its hydrodynamics during an extensive period of time accounting for the total available resource (ideally a complete year), must be conducted [15,29]. With this aim, the open-source code Delft3D-FLOW is applied, which has been successfully used for analysing the hydrokinetic energy resource in estuaries in previous works [8,12,14,15,23,27,29,33]. It approximates the conservation of mass and momentum equations under the Shallow Water assumption, along with the transport equation for salinity and temperature [38]. This allows the computation of baroclinic flows resulting from the mixing of river discharges and oceanic waters, which may be of interest in coastal bodies subject to large river flows [11,12].

In this work, the hydrodynamics of Miño Estuary are computed by using a high-resolution 2DH grid of 20×20 m of resolution which is interpolated to the most recent high-resolution bathymetric and topographic data available in this area (Fig. 2) (data obtained from Instituto Hidrográfico de la Marina, IHM, and supplemented by own data from survey).

Prior to using the model for determining the potential of this area for hydrokinetic energy exploitation, it is calibrated and validated against in situ measurements of flow velocity obtained from an ADCP (Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler) (Fig. 1) deployed for 8 days. To this end, the sensitivity of model results to the variation of different numerical parameters is analysed. The calibration process led to the turbulent eddy viscosity being set to $30 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$. In Fig. 3 the comparison between modelled and in situ x- and y-components of flow velocity, U and V , respectively, is shown. It can be observed that the model reproduces accurately the hydrodynamics in this coastal area, as confirmed by the various statistical parameters (correlation coefficient, R; root mean square error, RMSE; normalized root mean square error, NRMSE; BIAS; scatter index, SI) provided in Table 2.

Once the numerical model has been shown to provide accurate hydrodynamic results in Miño Estuary, it is used to determine the hydrokinetic energy potential. For this purpose, the main tidal harmonics (TOPEX/Poseidon database) [39,40], mean monthly river inputs (Confederación Hidrográfica del Miño-Sil, CHMS), and temperature and

Table 1
Hydrokinetic energy resource categorization.

Category	HE/IHE/i-IHE index
I	<1
II	$1 \leq \text{HE} < 2$
III	$2 \leq \text{HE} < 4$
IV	$4 \leq \text{HE} < 8$
V	≥ 8

Fig. 2. Numerical grid (a) and its interpolation to the bathymetric data (b) (the grid close the open sea boundary is not plotted for the sake of clarity).

Fig. 3. Numerical model results of flow velocities U and V against ADCP measurements.

Table 2

Validation: statistical parameters.

Parameter	U	V
R	0.99	0.99
RMSE (ms^{-1})	0.16	0.14
NRMSE (%)	7.66	8.61
SI	0.31	0.38
BIAS (ms^{-1})	0.03	0.02

salinity at the open boundaries (MeteoGalicia, Xunta de Galicia) are considered, with their values being set according to their intra-annual variation.

3.2. Available and exploitable energy resource

The available hydrokinetic energy power density at each time step, $E_a(t)$ (Wm^{-2}), is obtained as [13]:

$$E_a(t) = \frac{\rho}{2} [V(t)]^3, \tag{6}$$

where ρ (kgm^{-3}) is the seawater density and $V(t)$ (ms^{-1}) represents the flow velocity. However, all the available resource cannot be harnessed as a result of HECs only operating within specific velocity ranges. Thus, the exploitable hydrokinetic energy power density at each time step, $E_e(t)$ (Wm^{-2}) can be computed as [41]:

Fig. 4. Annual spatial distribution of mean E_e (a) and mean E_{ne} (b) throughout Miño Estuary.

$$E_e(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & V(t) < V_{ci} \\ \frac{\rho}{2}[V(t)]^3, & V_{ci} \leq V(t) < V_{co}, \\ 0, & V(t) \geq V_{co} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where V_{ci} (ms^{-1}) represents the cut-in velocity and V_{co} (ms^{-1}) the cut-off velocity, or the low and high velocity thresholds for device operation. In the present application, and on the basis of the characteristics of the current available HECs, V_{ci} and V_{co} are set to 0.7 and 3.1 m s^{-1} , respectively [29]. These values can be adapted, if required, in forthcoming applications of the i-IHE index, based on future technological developments.

Thus, the mean non-exploitable power density, E_{ne} (Wm^{-2}) is obtained as:

$$E_{ne} = E_a - E_e, \quad (8)$$

where E_a and E_e stand for the mean available and mean exploitable power density over a representative time period, respectively.

The resulting spatial distribution of the mean annual E_e and E_{ne} in the Miño Estuary are plotted in Fig. 4. The overall significantly larger figures of E_e , ranging from 0.5 to 1 kWm^{-2} at the potential sites of interest, than E_{ne} , of about 0.02–0.1 kWm^{-2} , indicates that the lion's share of the available resource can be harnessed. Finally, as it is the case of other coastal areas of interest for hydrokinetic energy exploitation, the differences between E_e and E_{ne} are larger in the areas with greater resource [29].

3.3. Reference energy and categorization

The last step for computing the HE index is non-dimensionalising E_e with E_{ref} according to Eq. (2). E_{ref} , which represents the threshold value required for energy exploitation, is set based on a thorough analysis of previous proposed hydrokinetic projects. A value 0.2 kWm^{-2} is retained, resulting in the five energy categories defined previously (Table 1) [29].

In Fig. 5, the spatial distribution of the HE index within Miño Estuary is plotted, with indication of the areas where $\text{HE} \geq 1$ (i.e., areas suitable for hydrokinetic energy exploitation). The resulting values of the mean value of the HE index within the selected areas of interest, HE_{mean} , along with their resulting categorization and total available surface are provided in Table 3.

Fig. 5. Spatial distribution of the HE index throughout Miño Estuary.

Table 3

Categorization of areas of potential interest based on the HE index ($\text{HE} \geq 1$).

Area	HE_{mean}	Category	Surface (hm^2)
I	2.04	III	17.30
II	1.81	II	17.98
III	1.44	II	12.53
IV	2.98	III	8.09
V	1.32	II	4.28

The area with the largest energy potential is Area IV, with $\text{HE}_{\text{mean}} = 2.98$ (category III), followed with a somewhat lower resource by Areas I and II, with $\text{HE}_{\text{mean}} = 2.04$ and $\text{HE}_{\text{mean}} = 1.81$, respectively (category III and II, respectively), and finally, with significantly lower resource and near to the viability threshold of energy potential, Areas III and V, with $\text{HE}_{\text{mean}} = 1.43$ and $\text{HE}_{\text{mean}} = 1.32$, respectively (category II).

4. Intra-annual hydrokinetic energy resource index (i-HE)

The hydrokinetic energy resource in a coastal body may be subject to a marked intra-annual variability, resulting from river discharge variations [14,34,42], and to a lesser extent, tidal variability [43–45], which in turn, as previously stated, may affect the exploitation of the hydrokinetic energy resource. The usual approach to consider these effects is by following a temporal characterization, i.e., by comparing different scenarios while considering characteristic seasonal river discharges and thermohaline conditions at open boundaries [7,14,33,34]. However, the resulting variability usually does not show a homogeneous spatial distribution, primarily resulting from the complex geomorphology of estuarine areas, and its influence on the resulting circulation patterns. Thus, the analysis of the intra annual-variability of the hydrokinetic energy resource should be conducted under a geospatial approach.

To this end, Fig. 6 shows the spatial distribution of the mean seasonal flow velocity, i.e., mean velocity during a complete season, V_m . It can be observed that there is a strong seasonality in the available resource, being winter the season with significantly greater flow velocities, in excess than 1.5 m s^{-1} over extensive areas in the outer, middle and inner estuary. On the contrary, summer is the season with lower resource, with areas with mean flow velocities greater than 1 m s^{-1} only present in the mouth of the estuary. The significant greater velocities with increasing river inputs indicates the important contribution of river

discharges to the total available resource in this area.

In order to fully understand the seasonal spatial variations in the resource, in Figs. 7 and 8 the spatial distribution of the mean seasonal E_e and E_{ne} are shown, respectively. As in the case of the annual figures, the larger figures of E_e than E_{ne} indicates that the larger part of the resource can be harnesses throughout the year. Nevertheless, the difference between E_e and E_{ne} significantly varies, but in this case not only throughout the estuary, but also during the different seasons. In effect, E_e attains values of about or close to 1 kWm^{-2} over different areas during winter and autumn, while during spring and summer, values in excess of $0.5\text{--}1 \text{ kWm}^{-2}$ are only attained at the estuary's mouth. With respect to E_{ne} , its intra-annual variation is also apparent, with overall larger values during winter and autumn, but with specific spatial patterns, which differs from the annual figures. In effect, the large river discharges may lead to strong outflow currents during the whole tidal cycle, even during the flood, which may exceed the cut-in during virtually the tidal cycle. This is apparent during winter with virtually very reduced values of E_{ne} (less than 0.01 kWm^{-2}) through the large areas occupied by the main river channel.

In this context, the significant variations in the resulting patterns may indicate intra-annual variations in the available resource going far beyond seasonal patterns, i.e., variations in shorter periods than seasons. To assess this, the time distribution of the flow velocity over a complete year at different locations of interest in the outer, middle and inner

Fig. 6. Seasonal spatial distribution of V_m throughout Miño Estuary.

Fig. 7. Seasonal spatial distribution of E_e throughout Miño Estuary.

estuary is provided (representative locations in Areas I, II and IV, respectively) is presented in Fig. 9. The results show that, in this area, and as a result of the presence of large river discharges, and the limited tidal prism, time periods of about 1 month are required for an appropriate characterization of the hydrokinetic energy resource. The key role of river discharges is also apparent during winter season, in particular in the middle and inner locations (Areas II and IV, respectively), where outflow velocities in excess of 0.5 m s^{-1} (cut-in of state-of-the-art HECs) are present during much of the season, thus explaining the virtually negligible E_{ne} figures at specific locations.

Based on the previous results, in the present work, the intra-annual variability of the energy resource in the Miño Estuary is geospatially assessed in terms of the i-IHE index as follows. First, the hydrodynamic results of the complete (annual) simulation are grouped in i 29.5-day periods (e.g., an annual scenario would result in a total of 12 complete periods), allowing an accurate characterization of the inequality of the tide during complete lunar months [46], in addition to the variations in river discharges. Next, the mean exploitable power density of each group of data (time periods) is computed as described in Eq. (7) at each cell of the numerical grid. Afterwards, the standard deviation, $\sigma(E_{e,i})$, and the maximum value of the energy resource of the obtained groups, $\max(E_{e,i})$, are computed at each grid cell. Thus, $i-E_{gp}$ is spatially assessed at each grid cell according to Eq. (5). To analyse the sensitivity of the

i-IHE index to the time periods considered, the $i-E_{gp}$ parameter is also computed by considering seasons as the representative time periods. To this end, the numerical results of the complete (annual) simulation are divided in 4 time periods corresponding to seasons of 88.5 days (three 29.5-day periods to also capture the inequality of the tide).

The spatial distribution of $i-E_{gp}$ throughout the Miño Estuary is provided in Fig. 10. It can be observed that the large river flow variations, as opposed to other estuaries with interest for energy exploitation (e.g. Ref. [33]), greatly affect the exploitation of the hydrokinetic energy resource in this coastal area, with values significantly lower than 1, ranging between 0.5 and 0.75 in most of the areas with potential interest for energy exploitation. The consideration of larger periods (seasons) leads to overall larger penalizations, which results from an over-estimation of the standard deviation of the exploitable resource (larger variations between periods if seasons are considered instead of 29.5-day periods), along with a larger value of the normalizing maximum value. Thus, in the present study it is found that considering 29.5-day periods instead of seasons leads to more accurate results.

Based on the results for $i-E_{gp}$, it is straightforward to obtain the spatial distribution of i-HE following Eq. (4). The results are shown in Fig. 11 with indication of the areas where $i-HE \geq 1$ (i.e., areas suitable for hydrokinetic energy exploitation). The resulting figures of mean value of $i-E_{gp}$, $i-E_{gp,mean}$, and the mean value of i-HE, $i-HE_{mean}$,

Fig. 8. Seasonal spatial distribution of E_{ne} throughout Miño Estuary.

within the selected areas of interest, along with their resulting categorization and total available surface are provided in Table 4.

The area with the largest energy potential is Area IV, with $i\text{-HE}_{\text{mean}} = 2.30$ (category III), followed by Area I with $i\text{-HE}_{\text{mean}} = 1.67$, Area II with $i\text{-HE}_{\text{mean}} = 1.38$, Area III with $i\text{-HE}_{\text{mean}} = 1.22$, and finally, Area V with $i\text{-HE}_{\text{mean}} = 1.05$ (all of them corresponding to category II). All of these areas present a marked intra-annual variability, as indicated by similar values of the $i\text{-}E_{gp}$ function, between 0.62 and 0.64. Despite the significantly lower values of $i\text{-HE}$ relative to HE , as a result of the penalty function $i\text{-}E_{gp}$, the accurate delimitation of areas with greater interest from a resource standpoint for energy conversion as provided by $i\text{-HE}$ index leads to a smaller surface of interest, and therefore the reduction of $i\text{-HE}_{\text{mean}}$ values with respect to HE_{mean} is less marked. In turn, the resulting delimitation of the new areas and $i\text{-HE}$ values provide a better definition of the appropriate areas for hydrokinetic energy exploitation and their real potential.

Despite the interest of the abovementioned areas for hydrokinetic energy exploitation, from a resource availability standpoint, some of them may be not feasible for the operation of specific technologies, resulting from the unsuitability between their installation and operational requirements and the coastal configuration. Thus, and in spite of the objective of defining the most appropriate area for hydrokinetic energy exploitation irrespective of the energy conversion technology and farm layout, in the present application, 3rd generation HECs are considered (i.e., microturbines able to work with very reduced water

depth of approx. 1.0 m), as a consequence of the depth-limited configuration of the Miño Estuary. Likewise, the narrow cross-sections of this coastal area also limits the definition of feasible areas, which require a minimum width. According to previous works, which investigated the hydrokinetic energy exploitation in waterbodies of width-limited cross-section (e.g., inlets), a minimum width of roughly 150–200 m should be available [47,48]. Finally, besides water depth and width requirements, a total available surface of about 3–5 hm^2 is also required for hydrokinetic projects being commercially viable [49]. On this basis, only Areas I and II are retained for further analysis.

5. Cost and water penalty functions

5.1. Cost penalty function (C_{gp})

The next step in the computation of the $i\text{-HE}$ index is the determination of the so-called geospatial cost penalty function, C_{gp} , a function independent of specific technologies or farm layouts which relates CAPEX drivers and coastal configuration, and therefore its accurate definition allows us penalizing areas where energy exploitation will incur in larger expenses.

CAPEX refers to the capital expenditures of fixed assets, including [22,49]: (i) device acquisition, (ii) cable, (iii) foundations or mooring system, (iv) installation, and (v) grid connection. Among these, cable costs, along with foundations and mooring system costs, depend

Fig. 9. Annual time distribution of the flow velocity at the outer (a), middle (b) and inner (c) estuary.

Fig. 10. Spatial distribution of $i-E_{gp}$ throughout Miño Estuary considering 29.5-day periods (a) and seasons (b).

strongly on the main geomorphological variables (shoreline distance, l , and water depth, h) and are therefore used for developing C_{gp} [29].

A thorough analysis of state-of-the-art formulations for computing

these costs [22,30,50–52] leads to the definition of the so-called total cost function, c_{farm} (€) to accurately compute the total value of CAPEX which is function of l and h of a pre-sized hydrokinetic farm [29]:

Fig. 11. Spatial distribution of the i-HE index throughout Miño Estuary.

Table 4

Categorization of areas of potential interest based on the i-HE index ($i\text{-HE} \geq 1$).

Area	$i\text{-}E_{gp,mean}$	$i\text{-HE}_{mean}$	Category	Surface (hm ²)
I	0.64	1.67	II	9.64
II	0.62	1.38	II	10.25
III	0.62	1.22	II	3.11
IV	0.64	2.30	III	6.02
V	0.64	1.05	II	0.57

$$c_{farm} = \begin{cases} 196.96l + 10^6 P n_c [0.15 + 10^{-5} h^3] & (9.1) \\ 196.96l + n_c [159.65h] & (9.2) \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

where the expression (9.1) corresponds to plants composed of bottom-fixed devices, and (9.2) to floating devices. These expressions are functions, in addition to h and l , of the total power of the plant, P (MW), and the number of converters, n_c , required for attaining the total power, which in turn should be defined for each converter analysed. For further details on the specific components of CAPEX and their computation, the reader is referred to [29].

The computation of C_{gp} is based on the definition of a generalized form of the total cost function, $c_{farm,g}$, providing the average cost of a “standard” hydrokinetic farm solely based on l and h parameters. To this end, and based on a thorough analysis of the current trends and prospects of hydrokinetic technology [52,53], in conjunction with several proposed farms considered in Ref. [29], a plant with total power of 1 MW, along with eight different types of energy converters were retained. Thus, $c_{farm,g}$ is obtained by computing and averaging c_{farm} for the different “standard” farms as:

$$c_{farm,g} = 1.5h^3 + 34624.31h + 196.96l + 22500. \quad (10)$$

Based on this expression, the geospatial cost penalty function, C_{gp} , is computed as:

$$C_{gp} = 1 - \frac{c_{farm,g}}{c_{farm,g,ref}}, \quad (11)$$

where $c_{farm,g,ref}$ represents a threshold value of the penalty function (Eq. (10)) beyond which hydrokinetic energy operation is not feasible due to a large water depth, distance to the coast, or a combination of

Fig. 12. Representation of the geospatial cost penalty function, C_{gp} (Eqs. (10) and (11)) as function of water depth, h , and distance to the coast, l . Adapted from Ref. [29].

Fig. 13. Spatial distribution of C_{gp} throughout Miño Estuary.

both parameters. Based on the analyses of hydrokinetic energy farms in different coastal areas [54], $c_{farm,g,ref}$ was set to $h = 50$ m and $l = 7.5$ km. C_{gp} is plotted for a general domain limited by these threshold values in Fig. 12.

The results of the application of the cost penalty function, C_{gp} , to the Miño Estuary (Fig. 13) contrast with those previously obtained for the Shannon Estuary [29], where strong spatial variations are apparent, from 0.2 to 0.9. Being much larger and deeper, Shannon Estuary is subject to greater spatial variations in depth and distance to coast. In the case of the Miño Estuary, a narrow coastal body with limited water depth, leads to much lower penalties, with the lowest values of C_{gp} of

about 0.8 corresponding to the central channel, which primarily results from its larger distance to the coast, and to a lower extent, greater depths.

In the present application, and due to the reduced distances to the coast and water depth variations, the mean values of C_{gp} , $C_{gp,mean}$, for the three areas previously selected are similar and close to unity: Area I with $C_{gp,mean} = 0.95$, Area II with $C_{gp,mean} = 0.98$ and Area IV with $C_{gp,mean} = 0.98$, and with specific locations with virtually no penalization ($C_{gp,mean} = 1$).

5.2. Water use penalty function (U_{gp})

The next step for i-IHE index computation is to assess the compatibility between hydrokinetic energy farm operation and the surrounding existing or potential coastal uses. With this aim, the so-called water use penalty function, U_{gp} , is computed for the Miño Estuary. The computation of this function is performed according to the following procedure.

First, the marine uses and their characteristics in this area are categorised into socioeconomic activities and environmental uses. The socioeconomic marine activities considered are (i) aquaculture and fishing, (ii) shellfish, and (iii) navigation. With respect to the environmental uses, they correspond with Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) and Special Protection Areas (SPAs), both grouped into the Natura 2000 Network. Next, the value of the penalty function U_{gp} is defined in these areas, ranging from 0 to 1, meaning unsuitable and with no restrictions for hydrokinetic energy conversion, respectively, with intermediate values defined according to the characteristics of each specific marine use [55].

With respect to the socioeconomic activities, in the case of aquaculture farming and fishing, which in turn represents the coastal use occupying more extensive areas in the Galician estuaries, values of U_{gp}

$= 0.6$, $U_{gp} = 0.3$ and $U_{gp} = 0$ are used depending on the level of restriction (medium restriction, high restriction and unsuitable, respectively), that each specific use imposes on hydrokinetic energy exploitation. With respect to shellfish areas, these are considered as areas overall imposing a high restriction ($U_{gp} = 0.3$), which in specific cases can be considered as unsuitable ($U_{gp} = 0$) for energy exploitation, such as areas legally delimited for a specific use. Regarding navigation, two different aspects are identified: (i) the intensity of marine traffic, and (ii) the space occupied by navigation channels. The marine traffic intensity is analysed by computing the so-called vessel density term, v_d (hkm^{-2}), meaning a value of 50 hkm^{-2} or higher an area non-suitable for energy exploitation ($U_{gp} = 0$) [56]. The resulting values of U_{gp} in the case of areas with $v_d < 50 \text{ hkm}^{-2}$ are obtained by linear interpolation between threshold values ($U_{gp} = 0$ for $v_d = 50 \text{ hkm}^{-2}$ and $U_{gp} = 1$ for $v_d = 0 \text{ hkm}^{-2}$). Finally, the areas occupied by legally delimited navigation channel are assumed to be unsuitable $U_{gp} = 0$, with the exception of oversized channels, which can be considered as partially restricted, for which a site-specific analysis of the coastal area must be conducted to define their adequate limits.

With respect to environmental uses, SACs and SPAs are assumed to impose a very low restriction to hydrokinetic energy exploitation [57] with $U_{gp} = 0.9$. The presence of other types of special environmental areas should be analysed and U_{gp} values defined on the bases of their specific characteristics.

Fig. 14 shows the spatial distribution of the different marine uses in the Miño Estuary. Practically the entire estuary is included in the Natura 2000 Network, except for certain small areas, providing space for traditional fishing activities. On the other hand, navigation is scarce in this estuary, with only some marine traffic near its mouth.

Once the socioeconomic and environmental areas of interest have been delimited, the spatial distribution of U_{gp} is computed for each

Fig. 14. Spatial distribution of marine uses (in red) within Miño Estuary.

Fig. 15. Representation of U_{gp} (individual uses) for the different marine uses coexisting in the Miño Estuary.

Fig. 16. Spatial distribution of U_{gp} (combined uses) in the Miño Estuary.

individual use (Fig. 15) and for the combination of the different uses (Fig. 16) – for the latter, the most restrictive value of U_{gp} is retained where different marine uses coexist.

As can be observed, the Miño Estuary does not impose significant restrictions on hydrokinetic energy exploitation from socioeconomic or environmental standpoints, with values of U_{gp} of about 0.9 throughout the estuary. Due to the reduced extension of this estuary, in this work the different areas of interest are subject to similar restrictions, and therefore present the same mean values of U_{gp} (where $U_{gp} > 0$), $U_{gp,mean} = 0.9$, with the exception of Area I, whose limits should be redefined so as to exclude the navigation channel (considered as not suitable for hydrokinetic energy exploitation).

6. Integration of the results

The integration of the different terms previously obtained leads to the computation of the spatial distribution of the i-IHE index (Eq. (3)). Its physical interpretation, as was previously introduced, is straightforward: the higher the i-IHE index, the better the site for hydrokinetic energy exploitation, with figures above 1 indicating suitability for hydrokinetic energy exploitation.

In Fig. 17, the spatial distribution of the i-IHE index in the Miño Estuary is shown, along with its comparison with the results provided by the IHE index. The areas where i-IHE and IHE are greater than or equal to 1 (i.e., areas suitable for hydrokinetic energy exploitation) are indicated. The resulting figures of the mean values of the i-IHE and IHE

Fig. 17. Spatial distribution of the i-IHE (a) and IHE (b) indexes throughout the Miño Estuary along with the resulting areas: Areas I and II.

Table 5

Categorization of areas of potential interest based on the i-IHE and IHE indexes (i-IHE ≥ 1 ; IHE ≥ 1).

Area	i-IHE _{mean}	IHE _{mean}	Category	Surface (hm ²)
I (a)	1.60	–	II	6.96
II (a)	1.32	–	II	7.31
I (b)	–	1.91	II	13.00
II (b)	–	1.68	II	15.55

indexes, i-IHE_{mean} and IHE_{mean}, respectively, within the selected areas of interest, along with their resulting categorization and total available surface are provided in Table 5.

The results provided by i-IHE index lead to the definition of two areas. Area I (i-IHE_{mean} = 1.60) presents greater i-IHE values than Area II (i-IHE_{mean} = 1.32), while occupying a similar total surface (about 7 hm²). The resulting areas differ somewhat from those delimited as of interest in previous studies [14,37]. In the case of [14] only areas in the middle to inner estuary were identified as of interest for further analysis, disregarding areas in the middle to outer estuary. On the contrary, other studies [37] only focus on the analysis of a specific location close to the mouth of the estuary (Fig. 1). In both cases, Area II was not considered. The approach applied in Ref. [14] is based only on energetic computations, along with initial socioeconomic considerations, and thus does not allow for the accurate delimitation of all the areas of interest. In Ref. [37], only a specific location for testing site fulfilling specific prerequisites (adequate current speed, bathymetry, low environmental impact, distance to shore, proximity to supply installations to ports and concurrent activities) is identified, thus disregarding other potential sites of interest. The selected area corresponds roughly with Area I in the present work, occupying a somewhat smaller surface (5 hm² instead of 6.96 hm²).

The application of the $i-E_{gp}$ function to this coastal body leads to the computation of the i-IHE index, and to the selection of areas which differ from those obtained by the IHE index. In these smaller (about 50 %) areas, the larger exploitable energy, along with the lower costs and fewer restrictions for hydrokinetic energy operation, permit optimum resource exploitation. In addition, the consideration in this coastal body of the IHE index instead of the proposed i-IHE index would have resulted in an overestimation of the interest of the selected areas for energy exploitation, i.e., greater values of the index, and to overall larger areas. Furthermore, it is important to consider that Area II is located in the

middle estuary in reduced depths, and thus may not be suitable for deploying devices with specific water depth requirements (different from 3rd generation HECs). On the contrary, Area I is in the mouth of the estuary at greater depths, and thus qualifies as a test site of HECs, as proposed in previous works [37].

Regarding other specific characteristics of the selected areas which may affect the exploitation of hydrokinetic energy, the exploitable flow velocities (between 0.7 and 3.1 m s⁻¹) present a rather constant direction both during the flood and ebb, roughly aligned with the main SW-NE axis of the estuary, with mean values of 232° and 57° in Area I, and 227° and 47° in Area II (flood and ebb mean values, respectively, considering nautical direction, i.e., from SW during the flood and NE during the ebb). This alignment does not impose a restriction on HEC operation.

The final decision about the exploitation of the hydrokinetic energy resource in the Miño Estuary should be based on a thorough site-specific cost-benefit analysis study on the economic viability of the selected areas, which is out of the scope of the present study (e.g. Ref. [49]). Finally, climate change, and in particular sea level rise, will have significant effects not only on the total available hydrokinetic energy resource, but also for the identification of the most appropriate locations for hydrokinetic energy farm deployment. In addition, the resulting hydrodynamic modifications will result in strong implications for the planning and management of both existing and future hydrokinetic farms. Thus, approaches for hydrodynamic modelling under climate-change scenarios throughout the lifecycle of hydrokinetic farms must be established and used for final decision-making [58].

7. Conclusions

In this work, the novel i-IHE index is developed to select sites for hydrokinetic energy exploitation in coastal areas subject to high resource intra-annual variability. This index improves on the existing IHE index, which had been developed for delimiting the most appropriate areas for hydrokinetic energy exploitation irrespective of the energy conversion technology and farm layout. This index provides accurate results in the case of coastal areas with tidally-driven hydrodynamics; however, it does not consider the intra-annual variability in the resource. Consequently, in areas where the available resource presents high seasonality, such as estuaries with a limited tidal prism subject to seasonal large river discharges, its straightforward application could lead to ill-informed site selection.

For these reasons, in this work the IHE index is extended by developing the geospatial intra-annual resource variability penalty function, $i-E_{gp}$, which, once integrated in the IHE index, leads to the novel intra-annual IHE (i-IHE) index. The implementation of this $i-E_{gp}$ is not straightforward – it requires a thorough assessment of the intra-annual variability of the resource through high-resolution numerical modeling. To illustrate this, the development of this new function, along with the i-IHE index, are presented through a case study in the Miño Estuary (NW Iberian Peninsula), a shallow and mesotidal coastal region previously identified as of interest for hydrokinetic energy exploitation, and whose hydrodynamics are highly influenced by large fluvial inflows.

To this end, the hydrodynamics of Miño Estuary are computed by the open-code Delft3D-FLOW using a 2DH grid of 20×20 m of resolution. The results show that this coastal area presents a strong seasonality in the available resource, being winter the season with significantly greater flow velocities, in excess than 1.5 m s^{-1} over extensive areas in the outer, middle and inner estuary. On the contrary, summer presents a significantly lower resource, with areas with flow velocities greater than 1 m s^{-1} occurring only in the mouth of the estuary. However, a more detailed analysis shows that this coastal area presents an intra-annual variability in the resource which corresponds with time periods shorter than seasons. The strong influence of river discharges in the Miño Estuary is apparent by the presence of permanent outflow velocities in excess of 0.5 m s^{-1} (cut-in velocity), even during the flood, during a significant part of the year, leading to virtually negligible values of non-exploitable resource (times when flow velocity is outside the energy converter operation thresholds).

Based on these results, the intra-annual variability of the energy resource in the Miño Estuary is geospatially assessed through $i-E_{gp}$ by numerically simulating a complete year, composed of 29.5-day periods (an annual scenario is represented by 12 complete periods), which allows an accurate characterization of the inequality of the tide amongst lunar months, along with the variations in river discharges. The spatial distribution of $i-E_{gp}$ throughout the Miño Estuary shows that the large river flows and their temporal variability, as opposed to other estuaries with interest for energy exploitation, greatly affect the exploitation of its hydrokinetic energy resource, with values significantly lower than 1 ($i-E_{gp} = 1$ indicates a location where the intra-annual variability of the resource does not impose any type of restriction or limitation to the exploitation of the hydrokinetic resource), ranging between 0.5 and 0.75 in most of the areas with potential interest for energy exploitation, and therefore leading to a significant overestimation of its potential for hydrokinetic energy exploitation in the case of consideration of annual scenarios. It is also shown that considering time periods larger than 29.5 days (e.g., seasons) may lead to an overestimation of $i-E_{gp}$. Based on $i-E_{gp}$ results, the spatial distribution of i-IHE is straightforwardly obtained, and a total of five areas of interest are delimited: Area I to V (all of them corresponding to category II with the exception of Area IV which falls in category III). The resulting areas based on i-IHE index provide a better delimitation of polygons with interest for hydrokinetic energy exploitation than HE index, which in turn leads to a smaller available surface, and therefore the expected reduction of $i-HE_{\text{mean}}$ with respect to HE_{mean} is less marked. Based on additional considerations of geomorphological restrictions for the operation of 3rd generation HECs, only Area I (in the outer estuary) and Area II (in the middle estuary) are retained for further analysis.

Finally, the i-IHE index is geospatially assessed by considering the remaining parameters in the IHE index: (i) the effects of coastal configuration on the installation costs (through the computation of the geospatial cost penalization, C_{gp}), and (ii) the socioeconomic and environmental aspects (through the computation of the geospatial water use penalization, U_{gp}). Area I presents the greater i-IHE figures than Area II (both corresponding to category II), while occupying a similar total surface (about 7 hm^2), closely followed by Area II. The resulting areas somewhat differ from those defined in previous studies, and also from those obtained by the implementation of the IHE index, in particular

Area II, which was not previously proposed for HEC operation. Finally, Area II may be not suitable for deploying devices with specific water depth requirements (different from 3rd generation HECs) as a result of the overall reduced depths in the middle estuary; as opposed, Area I with greater depths would be more appropriate for test site, in line with previous works.

This index overall provides areas occupying a smaller surface with greater energy potential than those previously identified without considering the intra-annual variability in the resource, where the larger exploitable energy, along with the lower costs and fewer restrictions for hydrokinetic energy operation will lead to optimum resource exploitation. Although this index was applied to an estuarine coastal area, it is important to note that it can be straightforwardly applied to any coastal area of interest with no restriction resulting from its coastal configuration or hydrodynamic characteristics.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

R. Carballo: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **D.M. Fouz:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **I. López:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis. **G. Iglesias:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported the PORTOS project, which is co-financed by the Interreg Atlantic Area Programme through the European Regional Development Fund [grant number EAPA_784/2018] and by ‘Axudas para a consolidación e estruturación de unidades de investigación competitivas e outras accións de fomento nas universidades do Sistema Universitario de Galicia (2023–25)’ with reference number ED431B 2023/17.

During this work, D.M. Fouz was supported by a predoctoral grant of the ‘Convocatoria de contratos predoctorais do Campus de Especialización Campus Terra’ with reference number 8042-272B-64100.

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